

KAAF UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
COMPUTER SCIENCE DEPARTMENT

RESEARCH PROPOSAL

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1.1 Title of Study

Implementing Web 3.0 in Ghana

1.2 Objectives of Study

To achieve our main aim, the specific objectives of this study are:

- 1) To determine if current internet speeds can sustain web 3.0 implementation in some areas in Ghana.
- 2) To determine the impact web 3.0 will make in the business and personal lives of individuals.
- 3) To determine the level of acceptance of the new technology.

1.3 Research Questions

- 1) Can the current internet speeds sustain web 3.0 implementation in some areas in Ghana?
- 2) What impact will web 3.0 make in the personal and business lives of individuals?
- 3) Will the new technology be accepted?

1.4 Supporting Literature

“The Web matures in its own unique way. From the static informative characteristics of Web 1.0, it progressed into the interactive experience Web 2.0 provides. The next phase of Web evolution, Web 3.0, is already in progress. Web 3.0 entails an integrated Web experience where the machine will be able to understand and catalogue data in a manner similar to humans.” (Riaan Rudman, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa, 2014)

The start of web 1.0 popularly known as the web was at the early 1990s where content on the web were created by first parties. You needed to own a server and have a lot of programming knowledge to put anything on the web. Almost a decade later in the early 2000s a new standard

of the internet was on the horizon with the introduction of services like blogger, Facebook, YouTube, etc. It was called the social web and was focused on user generated content. Internet content creators no longer needed coding skills to create content for the internet. It is still the most widely used internet standard.....for now.

Web 3.0 is an internet standard that focuses on data, knowledge representation, information extraction, data mining, information integration, and intelligent agents. It is called the data web or the Semantic web. Computers are given the ability to read and analyze data from humans and other computers. Computers will be integrated into everyday appliances like fridges, thermostats, electronics such as radios, TVs, electric bed even to automobiles in an initiative popularly known as the internet of things. Some of these technologies have already been implemented in various devices like personal home assistants which are basically devices that are always connected to the internet and waits for verbal commands to control other devices. It is also being tested in driving cars.

Most part of Africa remains disconnected from the world. According to 2011 estimates, about 13.5% of the African population has Internet access. While Africa accounts for 15.0% of the world's population, only 6.2% of the World's Internet subscribers are Africans (Internet World Statistics, 2011).

This is largely as a result of poor economic planning, poor forecasting and bad decisions.

These factors have crippled the economy and development speed of most countries in the region but with the implementation of web 3.0 into making the economic policies by using data it gets directly from the citizens to better understand the needs of the people and how to better use the Nation's resources to meet those needs.

“African companies can simply be very profitable by making the flow of information within and between businesses more efficient. Computers that understand speech and think fast like IBM's Watson computer will anticipate and find the answers to questions we haven't even thought to ask yet. That is what we call artificial intelligence and it works. Google is maybe the most tangible proof.” (Riaan Rudman, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa, 2014)

"Data is arguably the most important natural resource of this century," – Michael Dell

The sooner Ghana as a country and Africa as a continent start to utilize this already available resource, the better.

1.5 Methodology

This study will be purely based on qualitative methods. Due to this, the research first of will be looking into the sources of data. The data collection instrument to be used is a mini structured questionnaire which will be administered to respondents where appropriate boxes will be ticked based on unbiased judgments. The questionnaires will be issued to industry leaders that could facilitate the adoption of the new technology and also to end users.

1.6 Tools of Data Analysis

In other to assess the feasibility of implementing Web 3.0 in Ghana, primary data in the form of questionnaires will be subjected to detailed analysis. The data will be subjected to statistical analysis and where necessarily; graphs, tables and pie charts will be used with the aid of Microsoft Excel in the analysis.

1.7 Sample/Population

Population

The population considered in this study are the students at four universities in Ghana. These include:

- a. University of Ghana;
- b. University of Cape Coast;
- c. KAAF University; and
- d. Methodist University.

It also includes some staffs from various IT and telecommunication companies such as:

- a. Google Ghana;
- b. SuperTech limited;

- c. Ahonya.com limited; and
- d. Airtel Kaso.

Sample

For the purpose of this study, the technique or method of sampling that will be used is the accidental sampling method where questionnaires will be handed to some available persons at the listed locations.

1.8 Reference

- Internet Users Statistics for Africa (2018)
<https://www.internetworldstats.com/stats1.htm#africa>

- Riaan Rudman and Rikus Bruwer. (Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa). (2014). Defining Web 3.0: opportunities and challenges.
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